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ADAPT Centre's Feedback on the Draft Implementing Act to Establish AI Regulatory Sandboxes under the AI Act

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We support the objective of the Draft to enhance legal certainty (R-3). In our previous submission to the AI Apply consultation we show that the necessary, but broad provision to protect all fundamental right (FR) is a major source of uncertainty, especially for SMEs: https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/14625-Apply-AI-Strategy-strengthening-the-AI-continent/F3563742_en

We recommend therefore that the Draft be amended as follows to improve the opportunities to enhance legal certainty on FR protection compliance:

1) **Clarify that the involvement in sandboxes of national public authorities or bodies** which supervise or enforce the respect of obligations under Union law protecting FR, AI Act A-77(1), would be facilitated in Draft's provision R-16 and A(2c). For sandboxes operated by the AI Office, participation of the FR authorities should be clarified.

2) **The consistency of fundamental rights protections** in the use of AI subject to public law will be key to interoperability of trans-European digital public services addressed in EU Reg. 2024/903. The Draft should therefore clarify under what circumstances relevant technical specifications, e.g. FR-related data governance and risk management specifications, especially when related to interaction between bodies subject to public law and innovation actors that fall within its scope, can be used within a sandbox project.

3) **Fundamental Rights Impact Assessments (FRIA)** undertaken by AI deployers and providers subject to public law (AI Act A-27) may offer valuable input to sandbox projects involving such actors. The Draft should clarify the circumstance in which FRIAs can be admitted to a project and be shared with other participants as part of the sandbox plan (A-5).

4) **Sandbox project exit reports** (Draft A-6) can contribute to **regulatory learning** on and consistent compliance across the single market with FR protection obligations related to AI. The Draft should clarify how sandbox results that enhance certainty related to FR protections can be most widely seen and adopted. This should include where appropriate that elements of exit reports (Draft A-6 and A-7) that could contribute to *interoperable* technical specifications (e.g. definitions, classifications or taxonomies of risks, harms, treatments, or tests) are published in a manner that is findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable, including in a machine-readable format facilitating automated translation, consistent with principles adopted in EU Reg. 2024/903 (A-2(8), A-3(2), A-5).

5) **Academics who have researched issues in the scope of a sandbox project** may offer an important source of independent expertise that can assist in its effective conduct and reporting. The Draft should clarify the circumstances and terms under which academic experts can participate in a sandbox.

6) **Public procurement of High-Risk AI Systems** offers the opportunity for innovative providers and AI deployers to interact on agreeing the acceptable levels of risk, residual risk

and assessment of risk treatment in relation to use of GPAI in high risk AI system development and deployment and the implications for FR protection. Public procurement therefore offers a natural hub for resolving legal uncertainties around FR protections. The Draft should consider how sandbox projects can support such interactions and regulatory learning without compromising the integrity of the public procurement process.

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